

Updated Version of a Low-Cost Remote Device for Measuring Lightning Currents

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Abstract — This paper highlights the recent advances in the design of a low-cost device that has been developed for measuring lightning return currents. Updates have been implemented in both hardware and software to improve data recording, communication, and data reliability. These improvements enable measurements at a sampling rate of 10 MS/s over a 4-ms period, allowing accurate recording of first return current events. Results obtained from tests in a high-current impulse generator are presented and discussed.

Keywords — Return current, lightning, lightning measurement systems, lightning protection systems, lightning electric current, atmospheric discharges.

I. INTRODUCTION

The impulsive current that flows along the lightning channel right after the connection between the upward and downward leaders in cloud-to-ground events (CG), which is also known as the return stroke current, is the primary source of electromagnetic interference in power systems, whether due to direct or indirect interaction [1,2]. These interferences are the main cause of damage to power lines and low-voltage circuits, including telecommunications networks [3].

For most lightning protection systems, such as LPS of buildings [4] and shielded cables of transmission lines [5], several parameters of this current are very relevant for determining the best protection practices and strategies to be adopted [6]. These include peak value, specific energy, total transferred charge, maximum time derivative, and time-related parameters.

The acquisition of experimental data is crucial for developing more reliable statistical models of these current parameters, given the random nature of the lightning phenomenon. This requires deploying numerous sensors and dataloggers across structures of varying heights and shapes over many years [1]. Indeed, reference datasets available in literature have been obtained from measurements of lightning currents conducted at only a few research stations [7–13], which restricts the applicability of the available information in several aspects. In this context, the practical development of low-cost devices to measure lightning currents in different structures is valuable, as it enables wider deployment and faster data acquisition [14–17].

The design of such a detector is challenging, primarily due to the specific features of lightning return stroke currents – they can exhibit frequency components ranging from approximately 100 Hz up to 1 MHz, and the associated amplitudes can vary over a wide range. Thus, designing suitable sensors, signal conditioning circuits, and data acquisition systems for measuring lightning current involves several complexities.

In this context, this paper addresses the implementation of significant improvements in both the hardware and software of the low-cost detector presented in [14–17]. Its large-scale application allows for the construction of an extensive database that can better characterize the most important parameters for lightning protection systems design. As this new version becomes ready for installation, the deployment of at least 5 devices is planned in strategic locations within the metropolitan region of Belo Horizonte, Brazil, by the end of 2024.

The developments of this work are presented in this text according to the following structure. After this brief introduction, Section II presents an overview of the proposed solution. The first results obtained in laboratory environment are discussed in Section III, while the main conclusions are summarized in Section IV.

II. AN OVERVIEW OF THE PROPOSED SOLUTION

The new solution features a distributed sensor network that automatically transmits data to a centralized server, as illustrated in Figure 1. Compared to the previous version, the proposed advancements bring various improvements in both the architecture side and the corresponding hardware.

A key feature of this improved detector is its capacity to store recorded data locally before sending it to the central server. This temporary storage not only makes the system resilient against connectivity problems or communication disruptions, but also adds an extra layer of security and backup for the collected information. When the connection is stable, the data is automatically transmitted to the central server without the need for manual work or remote access to the devices. This simplifies the management and operation of the system. Furthermore, unlike the previous version, which required remote access to collect the data, this new solution automates the entire reporting process.

Figure 1 – An overview of the proposed solution

A. Main features of the local stations

i. Power system

Each local station is powered by a power source composed of a battery, a battery charger (or a solar controller), and an external power supply (AC or photovoltaic cells). This setup allows events to be recorded even in case of external power loss, as well as filtering any oscillations and disturbances that usually occur in the electrical network during storms.

ii. Data acquisition system

The data acquisition system deploys a STMicroelectronics STM32L476RG signal processing microcontroller, which is responsible for accurately digitizing the analog signal from the current sensor. It features a 32-bit, 80 MHz processor, 128 KB of SRAM, and 1 MB of Flash memory, as well as a 12-bit analog-to-digital converter (ADC) set to operate at 5 MS/s.

Several current sensors can be utilized in this detector, depending on the intended application. The device has been tested with Pearson and Rogowski coils, as well as with loop antennas. The signal from the current is driven through a signal conditioning circuit, whose 3D project and a manufactured version are illustrated in Figures 2a and 2b, respectively.

The signal conditioning circuit includes an integrator circuit, used in conjunction with the Rogowski coil or antenna. If a Pearson coil is used, the integrator is not needed and can be bypassed with a jumper. Additionally, it has a summing circuit to shift the signal, allowing the negative part of the events to be recorded, as the STM32's analog input works with signals from 0 to 3.3V. There is also an additional circuit for protecting against overvoltages and reverse voltages of the signal injected into the STM32's analog input. These circuits ensure that the analog signal is correctly conditioned before being digitized by the microcontroller, protecting the device from potential damage caused by electromagnetic disturbances.

The STM32 microcontroller was programmed in C using the Cube IDE, a proprietary tool from STMicroelectronics. The STM32's features utilized include two ADCs, a digital-to-analog converter, an analog comparator, SPI communication, serial communication, a timer, and a DMA (Direct Memory

Access) module, as well as some digital inputs and outputs for signaling and control.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2 – 3D Model (a) and a manufactured version (b) of the signal conditioning board

The signal digitization was implemented with two analog-to-digital converters in interleaved mode, resulting in a combined sampling rate of 10 MS/s. The result of this conversion is written directly to the memory by the DMA module, without relying on the STM32 processor, preventing this process from being interrupted during the execution of other processor tasks. The DMA module writes to a predetermined memory space in a circular manner, as depicted in the flowchart of Figure 3. With the help of the timer, it is possible to adjust via software how much information will be recorded before and after the trigger. The ADC has two output channels: one is used as a voltage reference for the trigger, and the other as a voltage reference for the summing circuit. This allows all these parameters to be defined via software, offering great versatility during testing.

The trigger is generated by the analog comparator when a rising edge exceeds the value set by the ADC. After the trigger, the post-trigger time defined in the timer is awaited, and then the analog-to-digital conversion is interrupted to allow data reading from memory. Next, the entire memory space defined for the DMA is traversed, and each value is stored in a text file on the memory card via SPI communication. After this operation is completed, the conversion process is enabled again, ready to record a new event.

Figure 3 - Flowchart of the STM32 code.

iii. Communication system

The communication microcontroller is an ESP32, which features a 32-bit dual-core processor operating at 240 MHz, 520 KB of SRAM, 4 MB of Flash memory, and integrated Wi-Fi (802.11 b/g/n) and Bluetooth 4.2/BLE. It is responsible for sending the data to the server, and ensuring it is securely and efficiently stored in the cloud via Wi-Fi.

During periods when the STM32 microcontroller is not recording, the ESP32 is enabled to query it via serial communication and check for records stored on the memory card, as depicted by the flowchart of Figure 4. If there is any data stored on the memory card, the STM32 responds to the ESP32 with a list of existing files. The names of these files contain the date and time of each event for subsequent archiving on the server.

Figure 4 - Flowchart of the ESP32 code

The ESP32 is connected to a GPS module that provides the time reference for the STM32 and performs the georeferencing of the device in the API. Upon identifying an available Wi-Fi signal, the ESP32 connects to the network and authenticates with the server. It then checks if it is already registered; if not, it completes the registration. This process ensures that the device is correctly identified and that the collected data is associated with the precise and accurate geographical location of the recorded event.

An electric field sensor can be used to enable the ESP32 to query the STM32 data only during the absence of storm clouds, avoiding competition with the process of recording events on the memory card. Thus, when enabled, the ESP32 requests the

list of existing files and, for each one, asks the STM32 to read the file on the card and send the data via serial. The ESP32 then sends the data to the server, doublechecks if it has been correctly stored, and deletes the record from the memory card. This mechanism ensures that the data is transmitted efficiently and that space on the memory card is freed up for new records.

B. Features of the server

The central server is implemented as an API (Application Programming Interface), following REST (Representational State Transfer) architectural principles, and is built using Node.js technology. This technological choice offers a flexible and scalable platform for API development, allowing efficient handling of a large volume of requests and simultaneous users. The information collected by the devices is securely stored in a PostgreSQL database, known for its reliability, performance, and advanced data management features. To ensure the security and privacy of the data transmitted over the network, access to the API is conducted via the HTTPS (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure) protocol, which uses TLS (Transport Layer Security) certificates to encrypt communications between the devices and the server. Additionally, user authentication and authorization are performed using JWT (JSON Web Tokens), implementing modern information security practices to mitigate risks of attacks and unauthorized access.

The API serves two user groups: the measurement devices and the clients who wish to query and analyze the collected data. The devices make “post” requests to authenticate, register, and store the events they record. They also make “get” requests to retrieve their registration information and confirm that their events have been successfully stored in the API.

During the project development, commercial software was used to make API requests and display the returned data in JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) format, simplifying the system testing and validation process. However, clients have the flexibility to develop their own front-end applications, tailored to their specific needs for data visualization and analysis, by consuming the API information.

PostgreSQL was chosen for its robustness, flexibility, and wide adoption by the developer community, as well as being a free market solution. Initially, both the API and the database were hosted in a local development environment to facilitate the development and testing process. However, both components can be easily migrated to cloud environments, offering greater computational capacity, scalability, and availability.

III. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Several tests have been conducted to validate each of the device’s functionalities, among which the most important are the analog-to-digital conversion, the trigger, and the memory card recording. The software parameterization of pre-trigger and post-trigger times, the voltage level at which the trigger occurs, and the voltage level for signal shifting allowed for practical testing in various configurations.

After the initial bench validation, further tests were conducted in a controlled laboratory environment. An impulse generator capable of producing 8/20- μ s currents up to 20 kA was utilized, with peak values reaching as high as 14 kA. The sensor employed for these tests was a Pearson coil, model 4418. Figure 5 illustrates the experimental setup.

Figure 5 - On-site tests.

Tests were carried out using a range of current amplitudes, including 0.5 kA, 1.3 kA, 1.8 kA, 2.5 kA, 5.5 kA, and 13.9 kA. The device accurately recorded the waveforms for currents up to 1.8 kA. However, for currents exceeding this value, the protection system of the conditioning circuit began to clip a portion of the signal due to the transformation ratio of the sensor employed. To capture higher current values, one of two approaches could be taken: either use a Pearson coil with a lower transformation ratio or adjust the gain of the signal conditioning circuit.

Figure 6 illustrates the current waveforms recorded by the impulse generator's native acquisition system and the detector for the 500-A current. The two waveforms closely match, except for a brief oscillation observed prior to the rising portion of the current waveform. This oscillation is attributed to a resonance effect in the circuit, caused by the electromagnetic field generated by the gap discharges within the impulse generator. This effect could be mitigated through the application of proper shielding for the cables and circuitry.

Figure 6 - Comparison between measurements.

IV. FINAL REMARKS

This paper summarizes the recent advancements and updates in the design of a low-cost detector for measuring lightning return stroke currents. The detector can perform both direct measurements using a Rogowski coil and indirect measurements through a loop antenna. Improvements have been developed for the hardware and software components of the system. Hardware modifications were necessary due to the obsolescence of components from the previous version, demanding the development of a new source code. On the software side, several enhancements were applied to the architecture to ensure improved network stability and reliability.

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